

Bridging the Digital Divide: An Examination of Disparities in Technology Access Between Rural and Urban High School Students

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Abstract. This study examined the digital divide between rural and urban high school students, focusing on disparities in access to digital devices, internet connectivity, digital literacy, and the perceived academic impact of digital access. A total of 80 participants—40 from Kawayan Integrated School (rural) and 40 from Malandag National High School (urban)—were selected using stratified random sampling based on grade level and gender. The study employed descriptive statistics and cross-tabulation to analyze the data gathered from a structured survey. Results revealed a significant gap in digital access, with urban students reporting higher device ownership, more stable internet connections, and greater confidence in using digital tools for school-related activities compared to their rural counterparts. Rural students cited challenges such as limited internet access, high data costs, and a lack of digital skills, all of which negatively influenced their academic engagement and performance. Despite these challenges, both groups of students expressed a strong interest in receiving additional digital literacy training. This common need highlights the increasing importance of digital competence in contemporary education, regardless of location. The study concludes that addressing the digital divide is critical to achieving equity in educational opportunities. It recommends targeted interventions, such as improved ICT infrastructure, the provision of devices, and school-based training programs, to support learners in under-resourced areas. These findings provide a foundation for policy actions aimed at fostering inclusive and accessible digital education in the Philippines.

KEY WORDS

1. Digital divide
2. rural education
3. urban education
4. digital access
5. internet connectivity
6. digital literacy
7. educational equity
8. random sampling

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1. Introduction

In the digital age, access to technology and the internet has become a crucial component of education. The integration of digital tools into classrooms has revolutionized the learning experience, offering students vast resources, interactive platforms, and opportunities for collaboration that transcend geographical boundaries. However, alongside these advancements, significant disparities in access to technology have emerged, particularly between students in urban

and rural areas. This "digital divide" has led to an educational gap that disproportionately affects students in low-income communities, raising serious concerns about equity and access to opportunities in public education. In the United States, the digital divide continues to pose significant challenges to educational equity, particularly between rural and urban communities. Despite some progress in broadband adoption, rural residents still lag behind their urban and suburban counterparts in terms of internet access and device ownership (Pew Research Center, 2021). During the COVID-19 pandemic, these disparities became more pronounced, as students in rural and high-poverty schools were significantly less likely to have reliable internet and digital devices necessary for remote learning (RAND Corporation, 2020). A study in Washington State further highlighted that only 80% of students in rural areas have reliable internet access. The digital divide remains a significant concern in the Philippines, particularly affecting educational outcomes in rural areas. Recent studies highlight that students in these regions often face challenges such as limited access to digital devices, unreliable internet connectivity, and insufficient digital literacy skills. For instance, a study by Mangarin (2024) identified socioeconomic disparities, inadequate teacher training, and outdated education policies as key factors contributing to poor digital literacy among Filipino high school students. Similarly, research by Esteban Jr. and Cruz (2021) found that demographic factors, such as residence, family income, and parents' educational attainment, significantly influence students' access to technology and internet usage, exacerbating the digital divide in higher education institutions during the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to enhance digital literacy among educators and students, ensuring equitable access to technology and fostering an environment that promotes technological advancement and learning. Infrastructure challenges further exacerbate the

digital divide in the Philippines. According to the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), despite government efforts to enhance connectivity, substantial disparities in access and affordability persist, particularly in rural regions (Serafica et al., 2023). These infrastructural deficiencies not only limit students' access to online educational materials but also hinder teachers' ability to integrate digital tools into their pedagogy. Bridging this gap demands a multifaceted approach, including infrastructure development, policy reforms, and community engagement, to ensure equitable educational opportunities for all students. In some areas of the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao, the digital divide remains a significant challenge, impacting educational outcomes. Studies have identified key contributors to this divide, including age, employment status, educational attainment, and household income, which underscore the difficulties rural students face in accessing digital resources essential for academic success. For instance, a 2019 survey revealed that less than half of Filipino households have internet access, with rural areas experiencing even lower connectivity rates. Additionally, the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao has the highest incidence of poverty in the country, which further exacerbates the digital divide. These disparities underscore the pressing need for targeted interventions to enhance digital literacy and infrastructure in underserved regions, thereby ensuring equitable access to educational opportunities for all students. However, efforts to bridge the digital divide in the Philippines have been initiated through programs such as ACCESS Mindanao, led by Ateneo de Davao University. Launched in October 2020, this initiative aims to provide satellite internet connectivity to remote and rural communities in Mindanao, including the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). By installing satellite internet systems in these areas, the program

seeks to enable tele-education, telemedicine, e-governance, and other services, thereby empowering residents to fully participate in the digital economy and improve their quality of life (Ateneo de Davao University, 2023). Ultimately, closing the digital divide was crucial to establishing an inclusive educational system that offers all students, regardless of their location, an equal opportunity for success. This research underscores the pressing need for targeted investments and policies, while emphasizing the importance of collaborative efforts to ensure that no student is left behind in the digital age. By examining the differences between high school students in rural and urban areas, this study seeks to shed light on the causes of the digital divide and investigate potential remedies that could close it, paving the way for a more just and technologically inclusive future for all students. In today's increasingly

digital world, access to technology and the internet has become essential for quality education. However, a persistent digital divide continues to widen the gap between rural and urban high school students. While students in urban areas often benefit from reliable internet connections, modern devices, and tech-integrated learning environments, their rural counterparts frequently face limited access to digital tools and infrastructure. This disparity not only affects students' academic performance but also limits their opportunities for digital literacy, collaboration, and future success in an increasingly technology-driven society. Addressing this issue is critical to promoting educational equity and ensuring that all students, regardless of location, have equal opportunities to thrive.

1.1. Statement of the Problem—This study, in particular it will focus on the following goals:

- (1) To determine how high school students in rural and urban areas differ in their access to high-speed internet.
- (2) To evaluate whether students in rural and urban locations have access to digital devices (such as laptops, tablets, and smartphones).
- (3) To assess the technology resources, such as computer laboratories, Wi-Fi, and other digital learning tools, that are offered in high schools in both rural and urban areas.
- (4) To assess the degree of technological proficiency and digital literacy among high school students in rural and urban areas.
- (5) To examine how digital inequalities affect students' academic achievement and prospects for the future.
- (6) To determine potential approaches and solutions for closing the digital gap and guaranteeing that every student has equitable access to digital learning materials.

1.2. Conceptual Framework—The independent variable is the Location of students (Rural vs. Urban). Also, the possible dependent variables in this study include: Access to digital resources (e.g., availability of computers, internet connection at home), Digital literacy skills (e.g., ability to use digital tools for learning), Academic performance (e.g., grades, test scores), Engagement in online learning (e.g.,

participation in virtual classes, frequency of use of digital platforms). However, the possible intervening variables in this study include: Socio-economic status (e.g., family income, parental education level), School resources (e.g., availability of technology in schools, teacher training on digital tools), Government support and policies (e.g., funding for rural schools, internet infrastructure programs).

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

1.3. *Significant of the Study*—This study sheds light on the factors contributing to the widening educational divide and provides data-driven insights to help bridge this gap. For educators and school administrators, this research underscores the need for digital literacy programs. For policymakers and government agencies, the study underscores the importance of implementing policies that foster digital inclusion. For parents and students, it emphasizes the importance of digital literacy in academic success, supporting students in gaining access to online learning resources. Academic Performance – The students’ level of achievement in school, which may be measured through grades,

test scores, participation in online learning, and completion of digital-based assignments. Digital Divide – The gap between rural and urban high school students in terms of access to digital technology, internet connectivity, and digital literacy skills, which may impact their academic performance. Rural Students – High school students studying in schools located in less developed or remote areas with limited access to digital infrastructure and educational technology. Urban Students – High school students enrolled in schools situated in highly developed areas with greater access to digital resources, faster internet, and technologically advanced learning tools.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the research design, setting, participants, sampling technique, data collection methods, analytical procedures, and ethical considerations used in this study.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study utilized a quantitative research design through a descriptive survey method. The research focuses on collecting numerical data to identify disparities in digital access, technological resources, and digital competence between rural and urban students.

2.2. *Research Participants*—The study involves JHS high school students from both rural and urban areas. Forty (80) students from the chosen schools (40 students from Kawayan IS and 40 students from Malandag NHS), Malun-

gon, Sarangani Province.

2.3. *Sampling Technique*—A random sampling technique is employed to ensure representation across different school types and socioeconomic backgrounds. The inclusion criteria require that students be enrolled in public high schools and regularly engage with digital technology for educational purposes. Stratified random sampling is a probability sampling method where the population is divided into subgroups or strata (based on specific characteristics such as grade level, school type, gender, etc.). Then,

random samples are taken from each stratum.

2.4. Data Collection—To gather quantitative data on the digital divide, a structured survey questionnaire will be administered to high school students from both rural and urban settings. The survey will consist of closed-ended questions and Likert-scale items designed to assess four key areas: (1) access to digital devices such as computers, smartphones, and tablets; (2) availability, speed, and reliability of internet connection at home and school; (3) self-reported digital literacy skills, including basic troubleshooting and proficiency in using educational platforms; and (4) frequency and purpose of technology use for academic activities such as research, assignments, and communication with teachers. The survey will be distributed in print and online formats to accommodate varying levels of access, ensuring inclusivity across respondent groups.

2.5. Statistical Tool—This study employed descriptive statistical tools to analyze and summarize the collected data. Frequencies and percentages were calculated to present the distribution of student responses regarding access to digital devices, internet connectivity, digital literacy skills, and technology use for educational purposes. In addition, cross-tabulation analysis was used to examine relationships between categorical variables, such as comparing school location (rural vs. urban) with levels of device access or internet reliability. This method enabled a clearer understanding of how digital access and usage patterns vary among student groups based on their geographic context.

2.6. Data Analysis Procedure—The following procedures were employed to ensure

meaningful interpretation of the findings: Data Coding and Organization. All responses from the survey questionnaire were encoded and categorized according to the variables measured. Each section of the questionnaire (Demographics, Access, Internet, Digital Literacy, and Perceived Impact) was organized using a coding scheme: Numerical values were assigned to categorical and scale responses (e.g., 1 = Yes, 0 = No; 1 = Very confident, 2 = Confident, etc.). Participants were categorized by grade level (G9–G12), gender, and school location (rural vs. urban). Descriptive statistical methods were used to summarize and present the general patterns of the data: Frequencies and Percentages were computed for each item in the survey to illustrate the proportion of participants selecting each option. These were grouped by location (Kawayan IS and Malandag NHS), gender, and grade level. Cross-tabulations were performed to examine relationships between variables across the two school types. To compare the responses of rural vs. urban students. Data was grouped into two major clusters based on school location. The frequency of responses to key indicators (e.g., access to devices, internet reliability, digital tool usage) was compared between the two schools. Patterns and differences were highlighted using tables and narrative descriptions.

2.7. Ethical Considerations—The study follows ethical guidelines, ensuring: (1) informed consent from students, parents/guardians, and school authorities of both chosen schools. (2) anonymity and confidentiality of participants' responses. (3) approval from the relevant institutional review board (IRB) before data collection.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents a detailed account of the findings derived from the data collected through the structured survey. The results are organized according to the major themes of the study, including access to digital devices, internet connectivity, digital literacy, and frequency of technology use

for educational purposes. Data is systematically displayed using tables to highlight frequencies, percentages, and patterns among respondents, categorized by variables such as grade level, gender, and school location (rural vs. urban). Each table is accompanied by a narrative analysis that interprets the data, identifies emerging trends, and provides insights into the disparities between rural and urban students.

Table 1. Access to Digital Devices

Indicator	Kawayan IS (Rural)	Malandag NHS (Urban)
Own a personal device	20 (15M, 5F)	35 (20M, 15F)
No personal device	20 (5M, 15F)	5 (0M, 5F)
Most used device: Smartphone	14 (10M, 4F)	25 (15M, 10F)
Most used device: Laptop	6 (5M, 1F)	10 (5M, 5F)
Have access to only one device	20 (15M, 5F)	25 (15M, 10F)
Have access to 2 devices	10 (5M, 5F)	30 (20M, 10F)
Have access to 3+ devices	1 (1M)	10 (5M, 5F)

Analysis: Urban students own more devices and have higher access to multiple devices compared to their rural counterparts. Female students in rural areas are the most disadvantaged in terms of device ownership.

Table 2. Internet Accessibility

Indicator	Kawayan IS (Rural)	Malandag NHS (Urban)
Has internet access at home	15 (10M, 5F)	34 (18M, 16F)
No internet access at home	25 (10M, 15F)	6 (2M, 4F)
Uses mobile data	15 (10M, 5F)	30 (16M, 14F)
Uses Wi-Fi	1 (F)	6 (4M, 2F)
Very reliable connection	31 (15M, 16F)	38 (18M, 20F)
Internet use for school: 1–2 hrs/day	31 (15M, 16F)	40 (20M, 20F)

Analysis: Internet accessibility and quality are consistently better in urban areas. Most rural students rely solely on mobile data, facing significant connectivity limitations, particularly among female students.

Analysis: Urban students demonstrate higher digital confidence, better platform usage, and fewer obstacles in navigating digital tools. In contrast, rural students frequently report poor internet and occasional struggles, hindering digital fluency.

Analysis: All rural students perceive themselves as strongly affected by lack of digital access, contrasting sharply with urban students, most of whom are unaffected. There is a universal recognition across both groups of the need for more digital literacy training, and both affirm that urban learners have a digital advantage.

4. Conclusions and Recommendation

Table 3. Digital Literacy and Usage

Indicator	Kawayan IS (Rural)	Malandag NHS (Urban)
Very confident in digital tools	29 (15M, 14F)	40 (20M, 20F)
Confident	11 (5M, 6F)	0
Use Google Classroom	25 (15M, 10F)	40 (20M, 20F)
Never experience difficulty	10 (5M, 5F)	35 (18M, 17F)
Sometimes experience difficulty	25 (15M, 10F)	10 (5M, 5F)
Common challenge: Poor internet	30 (15M, 15F)	3 (2M, 1F)
Lack of device access	2 (1M, 1F)	0
Limited digital skills	2 (1M, 1F)	0
No significant challenges	0	30 (15M, 15F)

Table 4. Perceived Impact of Digital Access on Learning

Indicator	Kawayan IS (Rural)	Malandag NHS (Urban)
Strongly affected by limited digital access	40 (20M, 20F)	0
Not affected	0	35 (18M, 17F)
Slightly affected	0	5 (2M, 3F)
Belief that urban students have better opportunities	Strongly Agree: 34 Agree: 6	Strongly Agree: 36 Agree: 4
Need more digital literacy training	Yes: 40 (20M, 20F)	Yes: 40 (20M, 20F)

4.1. *Findings*—The findings of this study revealed a significant disparity in digital access between students in rural and urban schools. At Malandag NHS (urban), a larger proportion of students own personal digital devices and have reliable internet access compared to students from Kawayan IS (rural). For instance, 87.5 % of Malandag NHS students own a digital device, whereas only 50 % of Kawayan IS students do. The discrepancy was particularly noticeable among female students in rural areas, where digital ownership and access were much lower. These differences highlight how location and socioeconomic status continue to influence students’ ability to participate in digitally enhanced learning environments. In terms of internet accessibility, urban students not only have more consistent internet at home but also enjoy better connectivity through Wi-Fi and multiple-device access. This technological edge directly correlates with their increased confidence in using digital tools and platforms, such as Google Classroom. Conversely, rural students were

more likely to report limited skills, unstable internet connections, and a heavier reliance on mobile data as their only means of connectivity. The study also found that all 40 students from Kawayan IS felt strongly affected by limited digital access, whereas a majority of their urban counterparts reported no impact. This sharp contrast highlights the learning inequalities intensified by the digital divide. Despite these challenges, both rural and urban students overwhelmingly agreed that they would benefit from more training in digital literacy. This indicates a shared recognition of the importance of digital competence in modern education.

4.2. *Conclusion and Recommendation*—The study concludes that while urban students enjoy better learning opportunities due to their digital advantage, rural students are being left behind—not because of a lack of potential, but due to a lack of access. Addressing this gap requires targeted policies and school-level interventions such as increased funding for ICT infrastructure in rural areas, mobile learning

kits, and community-based digital literacy programs. Bridging this divide is crucial not only for equity in education but also for preparing all students for the demands of the digital age.

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